

Scientists discover an incredible association between number theory and evolutionary genetics

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Number theory basically is the study of the properties of positive integers, it is also known as the Purest form of mathematics. At first it was very difficult too abstract to lay on to the natural world. in these cases , the influential American number theorist Leonard Dickson says that these numbers are impeccable by any application.

And then more and more numbers theory discover unexpected applications in science and engineering from leaf angles the Fibonacci sequence to the modern encryption techniques depend on factoring prime numbers. currently researchers have established an unexpected link between number theory and evolutionary genetics and this work on it was published in the Journal of The Royal Society Interface Particularly the team of researchers (from Oxford, Harvard, Cambridge, GUST, MIT, Imperial, and the Alan Turing Institute have find huge connection between sums-of-digits function from number theory and a key quantity in genetics, the phenotype mutational robustness. this quality was established as the average probability that a point mutation does not change a phenotype. This discovery may have Important applications foe evolutionary genetics. Many genetic mutations are neutral, meaning that they can slow down accumulate over time without affecting the viability of the phenotype.

But the existence of these neutral mutations can cause an important question or what if fraction of mutations to a sequence are neutral? This property, called the phenotype mutational robustness, defines the average

amount of mutations that can also occurs across all sequences without affecting the phenotype.

There was a accurately a question that the team has answered . They had showed that the maximum robustness is proportional to the logarithm of the fraction of all possible sequences that map to a phenotype with correction whose given the ums of digits function $s_k(n)$, defined as the sum of the digits of a natural number n in base k . For example, for $n = 123$ in base 10, the digit sum would be $s_{10}(123) = 1 + 2 + 3 = 6$.

Professor Ard Louis added, the beauty of numbers not only lie in the abstract relationships it uncovers between integers, but also a hiuge mathematical structure that illuminates in our natural world and we consider that many intriguing new links between number theory and genetics will be found in the future.”